

EFFECT OF COSMETIC SURGERY ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF WOMEN IN ETIOSA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF LAGOS STATE

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<p>Keywords: <i>Cosmetic Surgery, Psychological well-being, Women, Self- esteem</i></p>	<p>Abstract: <i>This study examined the effect of cosmetic surgery on psychological well-being among women in Etiosa Local Government Area of Lagos State. The objectives of the research were; ascertain factors influencing cosmetic surgery on psychological wellbeing among women and investigate the level of awareness to cosmetic surgery on psychological wellbeing amo in Etiosa Local Government Area of Lagos State. The descriptive survey design was used in this study. The research instrument used for this study was a structured questionnaire by the researcher. The population of this study covered women in Etiosa Local Government Area of Lagos State where data was collected using purposive sampling technique. The Self-Verification theory provided the theoretical framework for the research. Collected data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Findings showed that Majority (50%)of respondents strongly agree to cosmetic surgery enhancing women's self-esteem; Findings also revealed that majority (31%) of the respondents agree to have come across media campaigns on cosmetic surgery; it was also revealed that majority (50.7%) of the respondents strongly agree to the media being an enabling factor. The study therefore recommended that women should be educated on media literacy to minimize external influences shaping their perception of beauty and that there should be Promotion of alternative methods of enhancing self-esteem and body image, such as healthy lifestyle choices, exercise, and mental wellness practices.</i></p>
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Introduction

Cosmetic surgery refers to a subspecialty that is concerned primarily with the maintenance, restoration and enhancement of an individual's

physical appearance through surgical and medical techniques. Cosmetic surgery could be defined as a kind of surgery to enhance the body's appearance in the absence of any disease,

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disfigurement or congenital deformation which can be a factor to improve the quality of the individual's life.

Cosmetic surgery history dates back to early 20th century when most cosmetic procedures were done to correct a disfigurement due to an accident or congenital defects. Cosmetic procedures were performed to improve body image or appearance which improved self-confidence and psychological state of a person. Afterwards aesthetic surgery became the surgery that were performed on the body defect but to enhance or change the nature of the body to what the individual wants. The past decade witnessed an explosion in the number of cosmetic procedures taking place in the world. Africa, Nigeria inclusive, is not left out in this movement. Nigerians have been going out of the country for aesthetic surgery. However, efforts are being made by Reconstructive and Aesthetic Surgeons within the sub-region to put in place the necessary measures and enabling environment for this new trend of surgery to thrive. It is on this premise that it has become necessary for cosmetic surgeons to evaluate the factors that will influence the practice in the sub-region.

In line with global trends, there is a surge in the demand for cosmetic surgery in most developing countries including Nigeria. Despite this, there is a paucity of research on cosmetic surgery in most low resource settings. Such research is essential because there may be cross-cultural differences in attitudes or reasons for considering cosmetic surgery. In addition, understanding these issues

is also important for the plastic surgeons, as there may be relevant psychosocial outcomes in terms of the delivery of quality cosmetic surgery care and patient satisfaction.

It appears that cosmetic surgery when used as a psychological intervention (Pertschuk, Sarwer, Wadden, & Whitaker, 2004) has a greater efficacy in subjects who are psychologically more stable aiding in decreasing shyness and anxiety, betterment of interpersonal interactions, and improving self-esteem, attractiveness and self-image (Ferraro, Rossano, & Andrea, 2005). Kellett, Clarke & McGill (2008) concluded that based on the psychological profile of the patient, it would be prudent to receive psychological counseling prior to treatment (Kellett, Clarke, & McGill, 2008). Subjects with a healthier mental status are better candidates for cosmetic surgery.

Statement of the Problem

Cosmetic surgery, or “body image surgery,” primarily aims to ameliorate patients' body dissatisfaction, with the hope that physical modifications will ultimately translate to psychological improvement (Pruzinsky and Edgerton, 1990). Despite this widely held motivation for performing these elective surgeries, medical professionals have limited knowledge on the psychological effects of cosmetic surgery on patients.

In Nigeria however, the practice of aesthetic surgery is slow-growing and not at its best yet. Three major factors have been known to influence the practice and patronage of aesthetic surgery which are the medical

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advancement/facility, patient characteristics, and media influences (Morait, 2019). In Nigeria, media influence though positive, can also be negative due to a few deaths of highly placed individuals, following aesthetic procedures (Agbo, 2018). Some other models and artists have given a media boost to cosmetic surgery. Hence, this examines the impact of cosmetic surgery on the psychological well being among women in Etiosa Local Government of Lagos State.

Research Questions

- i. Ascertain factors influencing cosmetic surgery on psychological wellbeing among women in Etiosa Local Governemrnt Area of Lagsos State
- ii. Investigate the level of awreness to cosmetic surgery on pschological wellbeing among women in Etiosa Local Government Area of Lagos State

Literature Review

2.1.1 Concept of Cosmetic Surgery

While the popularity of cosmetic procedures has risen dramatically in the recent years, it has been a common practice for over 2000 years now (Krueger, 2013). Initially, techniques of cosmetic enhancement were used for reconstruction purposes that were of absolute necessity such as facial injuries that occurred during wars including fractured noses, but later on became non-essential desirable procedures. The major boom that caused cosmetic procedures to become prevalent and prominent was the then-innovative use of Botulinum Toxin type A to reduce the appearance of frown lines (Carruthers & Carruthers 1992). Later on, during the early

2000s was when non-invasive or non-surgical cosmetic procedures such as filler injections, lasers and micro needles were introduced (Krueger e., 2013). With the advancement of science, technology and medicine, it is certain that the future of cosmetic procedures involves innovation that will make aesthetic enhancement more effective, painless and lasting.

Cosmetic procedures, plastic surgery, aesthetic enhancement; concepts commonly used by people to describe the same measure: an operation performed by a medical professional on another with the aim of enhancing the appearance of a facial or bodily feature. The most recent cosmetic procedures statistics reported a 7.4% increase in number of operations performed from 2018 to 2019 (International Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgery, 2020). In 2019, the cosmetic procedures industry grossed an estimated \$16.4 billion in the United States only (American Society of Plastic Surgeons, 2020). Some types of cosmetic procedures were found to have a direct effect on economical dynamics in the United States (Gordon et al., 2010). These studies evidently show the massive effect of cosmetic procedures on the individual and global level.

The Growth of Cosmetic Surgery in Nigeria

Cosmetic surgery has witnessed significant growth and popularity in Nigeria over the past few decades. This trend reflects a global surge in the demand for aesthetic procedures, but it is

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particularly noteworthy in Nigeria due to a combination of factors such as increasing disposable income, cultural influences, and advancements in medical technology.

Increasing Disposable Income: Nigeria has experienced steady economic growth in recent years, and as more Nigerians attain higher disposable incomes, they are more willing to invest in self-improvement. According to a report by the World Bank, Nigeria's GDP has been steadily growing over the past two decades, which has contributed to a burgeoning middle class that can afford cosmetic procedures (World Bank, 2021).

Cultural Influences: Beauty standards in Nigeria are often influenced by Western ideals of beauty. These standards emphasize certain facial and body features, leading many Nigerians to seek cosmetic surgery to achieve these aesthetic goals. The influence of Nollywood, Nigeria's booming film industry, has played a significant role in shaping beauty ideals. Popular celebrities who have undergone cosmetic procedures often set trends that influence others (Ogungbemi, 2017).

Medical Tourism: Nigeria is becoming a hub for medical tourism in West Africa. Many Nigerians used to travel abroad for cosmetic procedures, but an increasing number of skilled and well-equipped cosmetic surgery clinics have emerged in Nigeria, providing a viable option for those who would otherwise seek treatment overseas (Ajani, 2020).

Technological Advancements: Advances in medical technology and techniques have made cosmetic surgery safer and more accessible. The use of minimally invasive procedures, cutting-edge surgical equipment, and improved recovery methods have all contributed to the growth of the industry in Nigeria (Nwachukwu, 2019).

Social Media Influence The rise of social media has had a profound impact on the growth of cosmetic surgery in Nigeria. Platforms like Instagram and YouTube have become channels for cosmetic surgeons to showcase their work and for potential patients to view before-and-after photos and connect with practitioners (Nwafor, 2020).

Regulation and Accreditation: The Nigerian government has been working to regulate the cosmetic surgery industry by setting standards and accrediting qualified practitioners and clinics. This has boosted the confidence of individuals considering cosmetic surgery (Oladele, 2021).

The growth of cosmetic surgery in Nigeria is indicative of a dynamic and evolving healthcare landscape. While the industry presents numerous opportunities, it also underscores the importance of maintaining stringent regulations to ensure patient safety and well-being. As disposable incomes continue to rise, cultural influences persist, and medical technology advances, it is likely that the cosmetic surgery sector will continue to thrive in Nigeria.

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Psychological Well-Being

PWB refers to a positive mental state that reflects on the individual's cognitions, behaviors and emotions. It is manifested by a functional social life and healthy affective condition (Winefield et al., 2012). High PWB is related to feelings of happiness, life satisfaction and better physiological health (Huppert, 2009).

Following the suggestion of multiple theories of PWB, the common aspects were combined to form a six-factor model of PWB that is composed of six dimensions: Self-Acceptance, Positive Relations with Others, Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Purpose in Life and Personal Growth (Ryff & Singer, 1996). Self-Acceptance is positively evaluating oneself, affirming one's past self and viewing oneself from a good perspective (Chamberlain & Haaga, 2001), which is considered central for a high PWB. Assessment on individuals suffering from psychological problems revealed that a positive correlation exists between self-acceptance and PWB, and should be considered in the context of mental health (MacInnes, 2006).

Another study suggested that self-acceptance is associated with self-satisfaction, which contributes significantly to PWB (Garcia, Al Nima & Kjell, 2014). Positive Relations with Others refers to the ability of having functional, affectionate and empathetic interpersonal relationships including romantic relationships and friendships (Ryff & Singer, 1996); having successful and lasting relationships is a sign of

high PWB. Early theoretical analyses suggested that social support overall had a positive

Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Self-Verification Theory

Self-verification theory was developed by William Swann and notes that individuals seek to be validated by others and be perceived by others as they perceive themselves (Swann, 2011). Swann believed that individuals hold certain views and beliefs about themselves, which then guides their behaviors that are meant to elicit reactions from others that are consistent with their perception of themselves. This notion is considered to be the driving force behind self-enhancement including aesthetic enhancement. In the context of cosmetic procedures, self-verification theory would assume that individuals with positive views about themselves tend to act in a way that would confirm these positive views and those who are not satisfied with their appearance are more likely to act in a way that confirms their negative views of themselves. This theory emphasizes humans' need to maintain consistency and coherence between their internalized beliefs and the environment's beliefs about them. Originally, these views are formed based on observation: since childhood, humans notice how others treat them and base their self-views on these external evaluations.

Self-verification theory suggests that individuals strive for confirmation of their existing self-concept, whether positive or negative. In the context of cosmetic surgery among women, it

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could be interpreted as an attempt to align their physical appearance with their desired self-concept. If a woman seeks cosmetic surgery to enhance certain features, it may be driven by a desire for congruence between her perceived and ideal self. Achieving this alignment could contribute to positive psychological well-being by fostering a sense of self-acceptance and satisfaction. However, if the motivation for cosmetic surgery is rooted in a negative self-concept or unrealistic societal standards, it may not lead to lasting psychological well-being. The key lies in understanding whether the surgery is driven by a healthy desire for self-improvement or by external pressures. Self-verification theory could explain how cosmetic surgery, when

aligned with a positive self-concept, may contribute to psychological well-being among women by reducing the dissonance between perceived and desired selves.

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was adopted for the study. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire. The population of the study comprised women from Etiosa Local Government Area of Lagos State. A hundred and fifty (150) women in Etiosal Local Government Area in Lagos State were purposively selected.

Presentation of Data and Analysis

A hundred and fifty questionnaires were distributed and a hundred and forty-two questionnaires were returned and valid.

Table 1: Distribution Based on Age

Age	Respondents	Percentage
18-21 years	14	9.9
22-25 years	59	41.5
26 and above	69	48.6
Total	142	100

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2023)

Table 1 discloses the distribution of respondents based on age. It reveals that 14 (9.9%) are within the age bracket of 18-21 years while 59 (41.5%)

falls within 22-25years. A further look at the table discloses that 69 (48.6%) of the respondents were 26 and above.

Table 2: Distribution Based on Religion

Religion	Respondents	Percentage
Christianity	66	46.5
Islam	71	50
Others	5	3.5
Total	142	100

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2023)

Table .2 discloses the distribution based on Religion. It reveals that 66 (46.5%) were

Christians while 71 (50%) were Islam. A further look at the table discloses that 5 (3.5%) of the respondents were other religion.

Table 3: Distribution Based on Marital Status

Level of Study	Respondents	Percentage
Married	42	33.8
Single	62	43.6
Divorced	38	26..7
Total	142	100

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2023)

Table 3 discloses the distribution based on level of study. It reveals that 42(33.8%) were married,

62(43.6%) weresingle. A further look at the table discloses that 38(26.7%) of the respondents were divorced.

Table 4: Factors influencing cosmetic surgery on psychological wellbeing among women in Etiosa Local Governemrnt Area of Lagos State

Items	Level of Agreement (n=142)				Mean	SD
	SA	A	SD	D		
Low self-esteem makes women do cosmetic surgery	33 23.2%	66 46.4%	19 13.4%	24 16.9%	2.8	2.9
Societal acceptance make women perform cosmetic surgery	11 7.7%	42 29.6%	37 26.1%	52 36.6%	2.1	2.3
The media is an enabling factor	72 50.7%	12 8.5%	22 15.5%	36 25.4%	2.8	3.1
Physical attraction may play a role	83 58.4%	23 16.2%	12 8.5%	24 16.9%	3.2	3.4
Experiences or bullying can make women want to do cosmetic surgery	67 47.2%	22 15.5%	41 28.9%	12 8.5%	3.0	3.2

Personality disorders forces women to do cosmetic surgery	22 15.5%	15 10.6%	59 41.5%	46 32.4%	2.1	2.3
Cosmetic surgery are done to regain confidence	28 19.7%	32 22.5%	48 33.8%	34 23.9%	2.4	2.6
Grand Mean					2.6	2.8

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2023)

Analysis in Table 4 depicts that 66(46.4%) agree to Low self-esteem makes women do cosmetic surgery, 24 (16.9%) disagree, 33(23.2%) of the respondents strongly agree while 19(13.4%) of the respondents strongly disagree. Respondent’s opinion on societal acceptance make women perform cosmetic surgery, 52(36.6%) disagree, 37(26.1%) strongly disagree, 11(7.7%) strongly agree and 42(29.6%) agree. Respondents opinion on the media is an enabling factor had 12(8.5%) agree, 36(25.4%) disagree while 22(15.5%) of the respondents strongly disagree and 72(50.7%) strongly agree. 24(16.9%) of the respondents disagree to physical attraction may

play a role, 12(8.5%) strongly disagree whereas 23(16.2%) agree and 83(58.4%) strongly agree to the statement. The table also reveals that 12(8.5%) experiences or bullying can make women want to do cosmetic surgery, 22(15.5%) agreed while 67(47.2%) strongly agreed and 41(28.9%) strongly disagreed. 46(32.4%) disagreed to personality disorders forces women to do cosmetic surgery, 22(15.5%) strongly agreed whereas 15(10.6%) agreed and 59(41.5%) strongly disagreed. Also, 34(23.9%) disagreed to cosmetic surgery are done to regain confidence, 48(33.8%) strongly disagreed while 32(22.5%) agreed and 28(19.7%) strongly agreed.

Table 5: Level of awareness to cosmetic surgery on psychological well-being among women in Etiosa Local Government Area of Lagos State

Items	Level of Agreement (n=142)					
	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	SD
I know what cosmetic surgery is	39 27.4%	69 48.6%	13 9.2%	21 14.8%	2.9	3.0
I have read about it	43 30.3%	56 39.4%	33 23.2%	10 7%	2.9	3.1
I have interacted with women that have performed cosmetic surgery	49 34.5%	38 26.8%	25 17.6%	30 21.1%	2.7	3.0
I've come across media campaigns on cosmetic surgery	32 22.5%	44 31%	39 27.5%	27 19%	2.5	2.8
I occasionally stumble on contents talking about cosmetic surgery	57 40.1%	22 15.5%	43 30.3%	20 14.1%	2.8	3.0
I always interact with issues related to cosmetic surgery	61 43%	18 12.7%	52 36.6%	11 7.7%	2.9	3.1
I have never been exposed to contents on cosmetic surgery	22 15.5%	46 32.4%	62 43.7%	12 8.5%	2.5	2.7
Grand mean					2.7	3.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey (2023)

Analysis in Table 4.3.3 depicts that 69(48.6%) agree to knowing what cosmetic surgery is, 21(14.8%) disagree, 39(27.4%) of the respondents strongly agree while 13(9.2%) of the respondents strongly disagree. Respondent’s opinion on reading about it 10(7%) disagree, 33(23.2%) strongly disagree, 43(30.3%) strongly agree and 56(39.4%) agree. Respondents opinion on having interacted with women that

have performed cosmetic surgery 38(26.8%) agree, 30(21.1%) disagree while 25(17.6%) of the respondents strongly disagree and 49(34.5%) strongly agree. 27(19%) of the respondents disagree to coming across media campaigns on cosmetic surgery, 39 (27.5%) strongly disagree whereas 44(31%) agree and 32(22.5%) strongly agree to the statement. The table also reveals that 20(14.1%) disagreed to occasionally stumbling upon contents talking about cosmetic surgery,

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22(15.5%) agreed while 57(40.1%) strongly agreed and 43(30.3%) strongly disagreed. 11(7.7%) disagreed to always interacting with issues related to cosmetic surgery, 61(43%) strongly agreed whereas 18(12.7%) agreed and 52(36.6%) strongly disagreed. Also, 12(8.3%) disagreed to have never been exposed to contents on cosmetic surgery 61(43.7%) strongly disagreed while 46(32.4%) agreed and 22(15.5%) strongly agreed.

Discussion of Finding

Research Question One: What are the factors influencing cosmetic surgery on psychological well-being among women in Etiosa Local Governemrnt Area of Lagsos State?

Data gotten revealed majority of respondents agree that low self-esteem makes women do cosmetic surgery. Findings show that majority of respondents disgaree to societal acceptance make women perform cosmetic surger. It was also revealed that majority of responents strongly agree to the media being an an enabling factor. Data obtained rveal that majority of respondents strongly agree that physical attraction may play a role. It was also revealed that majority of respondents strongly agree that experiences or bullying can make women want to do cosmetic surgery. Findigs showed that majority of respondents strongly disagree that personality disorders forces women to do cosmetic surgery.

Research Question Two: What is the level of awreness to cosmetic surgery on pschological

well-being among women in Etiosa Local Government Area of Lagos State?

Data gotten have revealed that majority of the respondents agree that they know what cosmetic surgery is. Findings also revealed that majority of repondents agree to have read about it. Data obtained showed that majority of respondents strongly agree to have have interacted with women that have performed cosmetic surgery. Findings revealed that najority of the respondents agree to have come across media campaigns on cosmetic surgery. It was shown from the finidng that majority of respondents strongly agree to occasionally stumbling upon contents talking about cosmetic surgery. From the findings it was revealed that majority of the respondents strongly agree to always interact with issues related to cosmetic surgery. Finding revealed that majority of the respondents strongly disagree to have never been exposed to contents on cosmetic surgery.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that women of Etiosa Loca Government Area are exposed to cosmetic surgery.

Women in Etiosa Local Government of Lagos State indulge believes in cosmetic surgery because it enhances self-esteem.

Women of Etiosa Local Government Area have come across contents on cosmetic surgery from the media

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Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are hereby made:

I. Advocate for stringent regulations in the cosmetic surgery industry to safeguard patients. Additionally, educational campaigns can help disseminate accurate information about procedures, risks, and benefits.

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ii. Promote alternative methods of enhancing self-esteem and body image, such as healthy lifestyle choices, exercise, and mental wellness practices.

iii. Educate women on media literacy to minimize external influences shaping their perception of beauty. Encourage critical thinking about societal beauty standards portrayed in the media.

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